

REMOTE LEARNING IN TAJIKISTAN: ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

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Аннотация: Статья затрагивает проблемы, возникшие в сфере образования страны. С появлением коронавируса во всем мире в большинстве стран все перешли на такую особую форму обучения как дистанционное. Наш Таджикистан не стал исключением. Дистанционное обучение (ДО) — это совокупность технологий, обеспечивающих доставку обучаемым основного объема изучаемого материала, интерактивное взаимодействие обучаемых и преподавателей в процессе обучения, предоставление обучаемым возможности самостоятельной работы по освоению изучаемого материала, а также в процессе обучения. Оно доступно всем слоям населения без ограничения по состоянию здоровья, дистанционное обучение дешевле традиционного; график занятий зависит от вас самих, дистанционное обучение доступно из любой точки мира - достаточно только иметь компьютер и доступ в Интернет; дистанционное образование предоставляет возможность учиться, одновременно работая, т.е. применяя свои знания на практике.

Ключевые слова: очное обучение, заочное обучение, дистанционное обучение, преимущества, недостатки, технологии, процесс обучения, практика

Annotation: The article touches upon the problems that have arisen in the field of education of the country. With the advent of coronavirus all over the world, most countries have switched to such a special form of education as remote learning. Our Tajikistan is not an exception. Remote learning is a set of technologies that ensure the delivery of the main volume of the studied material to students, the interactive interaction of students and teachers in the learning process, providing students with the opportunity to work independently, to master the material being studied, as well as in the learning process. It is available to all segments of the population without restrictions for health reasons, remote learning is cheaper than traditional; the schedule of classes depends on you yourself, remote learning is available from anywhere in the world - you just need to have a computer and Internet access; remote

learning provides an opportunity to study while working, i.e. implementing their knowledge into practice.

Key words: full-time education, part-time education, remote education, pros and cons, technologies, learning process, practice

Today in the Republic of Tajikistan there is an active process of reforming the education sector, bringing it in line with the world standards of the Bologna process. If we talk about higher education, then it is characterized by a period of transition to a credit education system.

In this direction, reforms have been carried out over the past few years. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Tajikistan "On Higher and Postgraduate Professional Education" includes provisions that enshrine the relevant principles of the Bologna Process, including such as:

- providing a two-stage training system; introduction of a system of credit units;
- assessment of knowledge and quality of education according to international indicators;
- mutual recognition of diplomas and qualification degrees of higher education in Tajikistan and their comparison with world standards; expanding the mobility of students and teachers.

It was assumed that joining Tajikistan to the Bologna Agreement will increase the level of competence of graduates, their willingness to acquire knowledge on their own, and the desire for self-improvement, focus on changing requirements in the labor market and the level of social mobility. Therefore, our country is trying to meet international standards.

Along with full-time, part-time, evening and external studies, in our country they began to pay more attention to such a special form of education as remote learning.

Remote learning (RL) is a set of technologies that ensure the delivery of the bulk of the studied material to the learner, interactive interaction of learners and teachers in the study process, providing learners with the opportunity to independently work on mastering the material being studied, as well as in the learning process.

Modern remote learning is based on the use of the following basic elements:

- information transmission media (through mail, television, radio, information communication networks),
- methods, depending on the technical environment for the exchange of information.

Forms of remote learning

Remote learning, carried out using computer telecommunications, has the following forms of training.

1. Chat classes - training sessions carried out using chat technologies. Chat sessions are held synchronously, that is, all participants have simultaneous access to the chat. Within the framework of many distance educational institutions, there is a chat school in which the activities of distance teachers and students are organized with the help of chat rooms.

2. Web classes - distance lessons, conferences, seminars, business games, laboratory work, workshops and other forms of training. For web classes, specialized educational web forums are used - a form of users' work on a specific topic or problem with the help of entries left on one of the sites with the corresponding program installed on it.

Web forums differ from chat classes by the possibility of longer (multiday) work and the asynchronous nature of interaction between students and teachers.

Teleconferences - are usually held on the basis of mailing lists using e-mail. Educational teleconferencing is characterized by the achievement of educational objectives. There are also forms of remote learning, in which educational materials are sent by mail to the regions.

Pros of remote learning

1. Availability

Studying remotely, you can gain knowledge from anywhere in the world. You can study at home or while traveling, in a cafe or in the country - in general, wherever there is Internet access. That being said, you are not limited to a country or continent. You are free to study at any university in the world. This accessibility is the main advantage of remote learning.

Online lessons are held in two formats - either a pre-recorded video lesson, or a live webinar. Live broadcasts which are no different from the usual offline meetings - you can see the teacher and the presentation, ask questions, communicate with classmates.

2. Flexibility

In the process of remote learning, the student masters most of the material on his own. This means that he is free to choose the time for classes. For people who prefer to live in a non-standard schedule, remote learning can be a real boom. Also, this form of education goes well with work. Typically, online study times can be easily adjusted to fit almost any work schedule.

3. Saving money and time

An important advantage of remote learning is its relatively low cost. Of course, among the various online courses and schools, there are also those, the price of which is several times higher than the cost of contract day study at the university. But these are rather exceptions. For the most part, distance education is cheaper than daytime education. This is because organizations that provide training services do not need to

rent premises, buy furniture and equipment, and maintain a permanent staff of teachers.

Learning remotely, a person does not depend on transport. In addition to saving money, this allows you to save a lot of free time.

4. Specific knowledge

Remote learning gives a person a specific set of knowledge and skills. You get exactly what you pay for.

Everyone who studied at the university came across frankly unnecessary subjects that do not fit into the picture of specialized education.

Humanitarians in universities are tortured with mathematics, mathematicians with philosophy, and everyone is tortured with physical education. Remote learning is free from the excesses of academic education. And if you pay for programming courses, you won't be forced to run and jump.

5. Relevance of knowledge

In recent years, the prestige of traditional education has declined markedly. Many people with a university degree do not find work in their specialty. Graduates of technical faculties become managers in offices; former students of philology become sales consultants. Against this background, the prestige of traditional university education is declining.

On the other hand, the prestige of remote learning is growing. Today, a person who has studied a specific course remotely is in an advantageous position. He has more chances to apply knowledge in practice than someone who has been studying abstract subjects that are inapplicable in real life for years.

Cons of remote learning

1. Limited choice

Unfortunately, not everything can be studied remotely. In some cases, it is impossible to do without practical training under the guidance of an experienced mentor. Remotely you can study history or literature; you can become an excellent designer or programmer. But you cannot learn to be a pilot or a surgeon.

Perhaps the situation will change in the near future. One day, virtual reality technology will allow people from different parts of the planet to take part in joint laboratory work. When this happens, the list of professions and skills that can be learned remotely will greatly expand.

2. Lack of personal communication

Full-time education is valuable not only for the set of knowledge. An important element of offline learning is personal communication. Receiving a traditional higher education, the student cooks for several years in the seething cauldron of university life. He interacts with teachers and classmates in an informal setting. Such communication can generate amazing ideas and radically change the fate of people.

If Bill Gates had studied remotely at Harvard, he would never have met Steve Ballmer or founded Microsoft.

3. Absence of positive "side effects"

The fact that remote learning gives a person a specific set of knowledge can be considered not only a plus, but also a minus. By studying remotely, a person deprives himself of many of the positive "side effects" of an academic education.

For example, the process of taking notes of long lectures trains your writing speed, develops mechanical memory, and teaches you to isolate the most important fragments from the flow of information on the fly. All these skills are very useful in everyday life, but remote learning does not provide them.

4. Insidious circumstances

In the course of remote, learning, you are likely to face unforeseen circumstances that will get in your way. For example, at the most inopportune moment, your light may turn off or your computer may fail. And the Internet can go off right during an important online seminar, and you can't do anything about it. Remote learning makes you dependent on technology.

Of course, you can get stuck in an elevator on your way to university. But if you have already reached the physical place of study, there is little that can prevent you from gaining knowledge.

5. Lack of control

The lack of constant control from the teacher is a minus, which can be easily confused with a plus. But not everything is so simple. At first, the student may feel that the lack of control gives him additional freedom. In fact, remote learning requires strong motivation and rigid self-discipline from the student.

In the process of remote learning, you will have to draw up curricula yourself, and then monitor their implementation, constantly struggle with the desire to relax and postpone work for later.

Let's turn our attention to the history of the origin of remote learning. In 1969, the world's first distance education university, the Open University of Great Britain, was opened in Great Britain. It was named to show its affordability due to its low cost and lack of frequent classroom attendance.

Other notable universities with remote learning programs are the College of Cape Town (South Africa), Spanish National Remote learning University, British Open University Open School of Business, Australian Territorial Information Network. In the late 1980s, the availability of personal computers offered new hope in simplifying and automating learning. Computer training programs appeared on the first computers in the form of various games.

In the 21st century, the availability of computers and the Internet make the spread of DOs even easier and faster. The Internet has been a huge breakthrough, far

more than radio and television. Now it is possible to communicate and receive feedback from any student, wherever he is. The spread of the fast Internet made it possible to use online seminars for training.

There are many different ways of remote learning. For example, remote presence using the robot R. Bot 100. Now in one of the schools in Moscow, an experiment is underway on this type of remote learning. A disabled boy, being at home at a computer, hears, sees, and speaks with the help of a robot. The teacher asks him questions, he answers. In this case, the teacher also sees the student, because there is a monitor on the robot. At the same time, the boy has an almost complete impression that he is in the class with his peers in the lesson. During recess, he can also interact with his classmates. If the experiment is successful, it can open the way for a large project to introduce such a method of remote learning throughout Russia.

As a rule, in the case of remote learning, students are not required to be in the classroom all the time. Most remote learning programs and courses still offer face-to-face classes on evenings or weekends. These classes are optional, but are usually extremely useful in developing practical skills in students. Also, a number of educational institutions use short (one-two-day) outreach schools, which allow to gather students on weekends for group work.

With remote learning, a variety of methods of delivering educational information can be used. Several generations of the technologies used have already changed - from traditional printed publications to the most modern computer technologies (radio, television, audio / video broadcasting, audio / video conferencing, E-Learning / online Learning, Internet conferences, Internet broadcasting).

However, until now, in many cases, despite the emergence of technological innovations, preference is given to simpler methods. For example, in India, the use of radio for remote learning is-very popular, due to its availability to the majority of the population and the absence of the need for additional infrastructure, which makes it really open and accessible to the general population.

Many large companies are creating remote learning centers in their structure in order to standardize, reduce the cost and improve the quality of training for their personnel. Practically, no modern company can live without it. Or, for example, Microsoft has created a large training portal to train its employees, users or buyers of their products, software developers. However, some courses are provided free of charge or bundled with purchased software.

How does remote learning differ from traditional remote learning? Remote learning is mainly based on the student's independent work. At the same time, communication takes place only between the student and his teacher, and often in writing. Remote learning focuses primarily on the collaborative learning method in

groups. Joint group workshops, discussions and dialogues provide support and understanding to each member of the group. At the same time, the isolation, which is characteristic of remote learning, completely disappears.

The method of teaching in distance groups also contributes to the accumulation of knowledge, as students constantly exchange information. For this, there are special forums, chats, Internet conferences, where you can ask for advice or have a discussion with students who are studying the course at the same time as you. The virtual group gathers people who came here to learn how to work, -improve their professional level of knowledge, get new qualifications, new skills necessary for your further professional development.

All remote learning students have the same opportunities to actively participate in seminars. Discrimination on the basis of race or sex completely disappears in the atmosphere of interactive communication. As a result, the opinion of each student is considered and attracts everyone's attention. There is no need to travel to sessions and consultations. The indisputable advantage of remote learning is the possibility of regular online consultations with the teacher and the teacher's individual approach to each student.

There is an opinion that when you study remotely, it is easy to write papers and take exams - I copied and sent them. This is what the traditional remote learning suffers more. In the distance courses, there are no works that involve cheating. If a work is sent that has been written off (it is very easy to determine), then it will not be accepted. This is specifically stated in the instructions. When passing exams, it makes no sense for distance students to write off, since there are no traditional tickets here. In distance programs, tests and professionally oriented tasks are most common, in the solution of which it is even recommended to use a textbook and additional materials. The tests, especially the final ones, are often asked to answer in real time, and each question "hangs" on the screen for a strictly defined time. Didn't fit, got into the textbook or lectures - the question disappeared and is considered unanswered. And what's the point in cheating? You want to get an education, not a piece of paper. Distance education is focused on people who want to get an education, not a crust.

Due to the spread of coronavirus in the world, many universities, have switched and are moving to before and recognize it as the most convenient study in all previous times. Tajikistan also does not stand aside. All universities have switched to remote learning and the correspondence department will soo become a thing of the past.